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PRESCRIPTION PATTERN IN MANAGEMENT OF VITILIGO IN A TERTIARY CARE CENTRE; A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Vitiligo is an acquired disorder characterized by depigmentation of skin which affects nearly 0.5% of the world population without any gender or racial differences. The aetiopathogenic mechanisms of vitiligo are still poorly understood posing a hurdle in the progress in its diagnosis and treatment. **Methodology:** This prospective observational study was conducted over a period of one year in outpatient clinic of skin and VD department in a tertiary care centre to understand the prescription pattern in patients with vitiligo. **Results:** Tacrolimus and topical corticosteroids were found to be the most commonly used drugs in the study. Use of polypharmacy, generic names and drugs from NLEM was found to be less. **Conclusion:** The prescription pattern of medications was in accordance with the guidelines and recommendations for the management of vitiligo.

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INTRODUCTION

Vitiligo is most common acquired depigmenting skin disorder characterized by sharply demarcated lesions of variable size and shape. The lesions have the tendency to increase in size during the patient's lifetime. About 0.5% of the world's population is affected by the disease with approximately half of patients with vitiligo present presenting before 20 years of age. The disease affects both the sexes are equally affected with no significant difference in rate of occurrence according to skin type or race.¹

The histological examination shows complete absence of melanocytes in the lesions. Most of the patients experience increased sensitivity to sun exposure of their depigmented skin.² The initial symptom of vitiligo is most often a well-defined depigmented chalk white macula. The lesions may present on any part of the body but are usually seen on sites of stretch and pressure like knees, elbows, dorsum of hands, and fingers.³ The lesions often have hyperpigmented margins. Sometimes patients present with 'trichrome vitiligo' where hypopigmented lesions occur together with the depigmented spots with hyperpigmented margins in the same patient.

The natural course of the disease is usually progressive. After a rapid onset, the lesions show a stable course and after years of stabilization, a sudden exacerbation may occur. Complete depigmentation of the whole integument occurs within 6 to 12 months after onset of the disease. Spontaneous repigmentation may occur in only one or a few maculae and occurs perifollicular or from the margins of the lesion.⁴ Vitiligo is generally considered to be a cosmetic issue however it can be psychologically devastating. Patients often suffer from low self-esteem, inferiority, poor body image, and social discrimination affecting the quality of life (QoL).⁵

Efficacy of the treatment of the vitiligo is based on the assessment of the degree of repigmentation with more than 50% or more than 75% is considered a good clinical response although the evaluation of the repigmentation is not well standardized. A quantitative objective score (Vitiligo Area Scoring Index)⁶ and the Vitiligo European Task Force (VETF)⁷ score are commonly used. Narrow-band ultraviolet B (UVB) radiation is currently the preferred treatment for adults and children with non-segmental vitiligo. Ultraviolet B delivers peak emission at 311 nm. However this type of treatment needs access to a specialized treatment centre. Topical therapies, including corticosteroids and calcineurin inhibitors, may be effective in cases of non-segmental or segmental vitiligo in which the disease is localized such as in cases of nonsegmental or segmental vitiligo. Combined topical and ultraviolet-light treatments are often considered when there has been no response to phototherapy alone after 3 months or when the goal is to accelerate the response and reduce cumulative exposure to ultraviolet light. Quick but less stable diffuse repigmentation is seen with the use of topical corticosteroids and calcineurin inhibitors.⁸ A systematic review of randomized trials and case series showed that class 3 (potent) topical corticosteroids (e.g., betamethasone) were significantly more effective than placebo in treating localized vitiligo, resulting in more than 75% repigmentation in 56% of patients.⁹ Skin atrophy is not seen with the use of topical calcineurin inhibitors and hence they are preferred for face and neck lesions.¹⁰ Calcineurin inhibitors promote repigmentation without inducing immunosuppression¹¹ and their efficacy is enhanced by occlusion.¹² Various surgical methods such as minigrafting, autologous epidermal cell suspension transplantation, ultra-thin epidermal grafts are used in some cases of focal or segmental vitiligo if medical therapy fails.^{Error! Bookmark not defined.} Masking agents are often used on a temporary, semipermanent, or permanent basis. Self-tanning interventions may improve quality of life. Dihydroxyacetone (DHA) is the most frequently used self-tanning.¹³ Results with the use of chemical or laser depigmentation are variable which is often used in an option in a small subgroup of carefully selected patients.¹⁴

To promote the rational use of medicines it is increasingly becoming necessary to assess the drug use pattern in various chronic conditions such as psoriasis. The data on prescription for patients affected by vitiligo is limited; not many studies evaluated the use of different treatment modalities available for managing these patients. Hence the present study was planned to analyze the prescribing pattern of drugs among patients of Vitiligo in dermatology department of our institute.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was a retrospective evaluation of drug utilization pattern in patients with vitiligo being treated in the department of skin and venereal disease at Indira Gandhi government medical college, Nagpur. The study was conducted after taking approval from the institutional ethics committee.

This prospective observational study was conducted at the department of skin and venereal disease in patients with vitiligo treated from June 2017 to May 2018. The data was obtained from out-patient department record forms and the missing data was obtained from the health management information system of the hospital.

Data of all the patients with vitiligo was included in the final analysis. Data collection was done on a predesigned and approved case record form. Case record form included patient's demographic details, clinical diagnosis, and treatment prescribed. The complete prescription given to the patient was noted on the case record form. The data was analysed using Microsoft excel 2010 and represented as mean and percentages.

RESULTS

Baseline characteristics

Two hundred and eighty four patients received treatment for vitiligo in the department of skin and VD over a period of 1 year (June 2017-May 2018). The mean age of the patients was found to be 28.26; with 36% of the patient less than 18 years of age (n=102). The age range in the patients was found to be 1 to 87 years with 45 (16%) of the patients more than 50 years of age. Male to female ratio distribution of the patients was found to be 1:1.08.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of study population.

Baseline characters		
Total number of patients		284
Age (years)	Mean	28.26
	Range	1-87
Gender	Males n (%)	136 (47.88%)
	Females n (%)	148 (52.11%)

The study data for age and gender distribution was further analysed by categorizing in different age groups; the results are shown in the figure below.

Figure 1: Age and gender wise distribution of the study population.

The diagnosis was recorded from the out-patient case report and categorized. Vitiligo vulgaris (69%) was found to be the more common in the study population additionally 5% of the patients were found to be suffering from other skin conditions; tinea being the most common. Non segmental vitiligo was reported in 12% of the patients. Evaluation of disease pattern is shown in Table 2;

Table 2: Disease pattern of Vitiligo.

Disease Type		N (%)
Previtiligo		31 (10.91)
Segmental vitiligo		197 (69.36)
Non segmental-Vitiligo		34 (11.97)
Segmental Vitiligo	Tinea	10 (3.52)
	Melasma	3 (1.04)
	PMLE	1 (0.35)
	Acne	2 (0.7)
	Scabies	1 (0.35)
	Xanthelesma	1 (0.35)
	Impetigo	1 (0.35)
	Guttate Vitiligo	3 (1.04)
Total	284	

Prescription analysis

A total of 478 prescriptions were given for 285 patients. Total number of drugs given during the study was 1453 with an average of 3 drugs per prescription; ranging from 1-9 drugs/prescription. Generic names were used for prescribing 196 (17.02%) drugs whereas number of drugs from the national list of essential medicines was 42. detailed results are shown in Table 3;

Table 3: Prescription analysis.

Number of patients	285
Total number of prescriptions	478
Total number of drugs	1453
Number of drugs/prescription	3 [Range (1-9)]
Drugs prescribed by generic name n (%)	496 (34.13)
Drugs prescribed from NLEM n (%)	32/78 (41.02)

Evaluation of route of administration revealed that the drugs were either given orally (n=617) or topically (n=836). Assessment of formulation is as shown in

Figure 2; tablet was the most commonly prescribed formulation for the patients in this study.

Figure 2: Formulations of the prescribed drugs.

Most commonly used class of drugs were calcineurin inhibitors followed by steroids and Vitamins. Tacrolimus and Steroids were mostly prescribed as topical preparations. Vitamin B complex and Vitamin D were also prescribed to majority of patients in oral dosage forms. Immunomodulator Levamisole and photosensitizer psoralen was also prescribed in the study population. The class distribution of commonly used drugs in the management of study population is shown in

Figure 3;

Figure 3: Commonly used drug classes in the management of study population.

Tacrolimus was prescribed as topical preparation majority being ointment (n=376). The details of the different preparation used in the study population are shown in the table below;

Table 4: Formulation of Tacrolimus used in the patients.

Formulation	N (%)
Cream	19 (4.48)
Gel	4 (0.94)
Lotion	22 (5.18)
Ointment	376 (88.67)
Tablet	3 (0.70)
Total	424

Corticosteroid was another class of drug commonly used in the management of vitiligo in the study population; detailed analysis is shown in the figure below.

Figure 4: Prescription pattern of corticosteroids in study population.

DISCUSSION

Prevalence studies suggest that most of the patients suffering from vitiligo present before the age of 20 years. ¹⁴ Our study also showed that, most of the patients were under 20 years of age (41.54%) similar results were reported in a recently published evaluation by Mahajan et al where 50.6% patients were aged ≤ 20 years. ¹⁵ No significant difference in number of patients depending on gender is reported in various studies as observed in our study where male to female ratio was found to be 1:1.8; male to female ratio of 1:1.1 was reported by Mahajan et al. ¹⁶ The vitiligo vulgaris was found in 69% of the patients in this study which is more than 59.5% cases reported by other study. Non-segmental vitiligo was seen in 12% of the patients which has a reported prevalence of 5%–27.9% of all cases of vitiligo. ¹⁶

A total of 285 patients were treated for vitiligo in the skin outpatient department over the period of a year for whom 478 prescriptions were given. Average number of drugs per prescription was found to be 3 for a total of 1453 drugs prescribed in the study. Studies have not been done to evaluate the prescriptions in patients with vitiligo and hence such data is missing in the literature. There is large heterogeneity in the definition of polypharmacy however the most commonly used definition of polypharmacy includes use of five or more medications. By this definition the polypharmacy was observed in 18.07% patients with vitiligo in this study which otherwise is a common finding in drug utilization studies done for the skin conditions. As expected the most commonly used route of administration was the topical and formulations such as ointment was the most commonly used formulation. Overall, tablets were the most commonly prescribed dosage form of drug. Drugs prescribed from NLEM were found to be less (41.02%); by incorporating more drugs from the essential list of medicines can reduce the economic burden on the patients as these drugs are cheap compared to those not included in the list. Also the drugs prescribed by the generic names were also only 34.13%, increase in the practice of using generic name for the drugs can further reduce the cost of therapy.

Topical Calcineurine inhibitor, tacrolimus was found to be the most commonly used drug (n=421) in this study especially in ointment form (88.67%). Patients intolerant to topical corticosteroids have been effectively treated with topical Calcineurine inhibitor since 2002. ¹⁷ They act by affecting the activation/maturation of T cells and subsequently inhibiting the production of cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α ¹⁸ and also by enhancing melanocyte migration and differentiation. ¹⁹ Topical corticosteroids (TCS) have been applied since the 1950s for their anti-inflammatory and immunomodulating effects. Topical corticosteroid was given in 311 prescriptions which was second commonly used drug class in this study. As first-line treatment for limited forms of vitiligo TCS and topical calcineurin inhibitors (TCI) are now widely used. ²⁰

Monitoring of drug usage pattern combined with regular feedback to the prescribers is essential to encourage and facilitate rational prescribing of drugs. Rational use of available therapies in patients with vitiligo can minimize the systemic and cutaneous adverse effects associated with them. The optimum benefit can be achieved by taking into account parameters such as disease presentation with sites affected, age of the patient, and the pharmacology of the prescribed medications. ²¹ The drug use in this study was found to be in line with the available recommendations as well as various consensus statements published for treatment of vitiligo. ²²

CONCLUSION

Calcineurine inhibitor tacrolimus was found to be the most commonly used drug for the management of vitiligo in this study followed by topical steroids, antioxidants and vitamin supplements. Data on the safety of these medications as well as the compliance of the patients to the prescribed therapy can further add to the understanding of the effective therapies for the management of patients with vitiligo. Study also found that there is scope of reducing the cost of therapy by including drugs from the NLEM as well as by using the generic names. Moreover such type of studies on a further large scale will help in designing policy as well as giving therapeutic recommendations as those are lacking for the management of vitiligo.

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